

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of teamwork and work discipline with work motivation as an intervention on the work performance of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV employees

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of teamwork and work discipline on work performance with work motivation as an intervening variable. The location of the research was conducted by PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV. The number of samples in this study was 58 respondents who were contract employees of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV. The analysis method used is multiple linear regression analysis. The results showed no and no significant influence between teamwork on work motivation. There is a positive but not significant influence between teamwork on work performance. There is a positive but not significant influence between work disciplines on work motivation. There is a positive and significant influence between work disciplines on work performance. There is no influence and no significance between work motivation and work performance. There is an influence but not significant between teamwork on work performance through work motivation. There is no influence and insignificance between work discipline on work performance through work motivation.

Keywords: Teamwork; Work Discipline; Work Motivation; Work Performance

1. Introduction

Work performance has a very important basis for the company as a tool for making decisions for its employees. Employee performance is beneficial for employee performance improvement, compensation adjustments, placement decisions, the need for training and development, career planning and development, staffing process irregularities, informational inaccuracies, job design errors, fair employment opportunities, and external challenges. Work performance is very important for an organization or company to achieve its goals. In the context of human resource development, the work performance of an employee in a company is needed to achieve work performance for the employees themselves and also for the success of the company. Work performance is the result of work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him, which is based on skills, experience, and sincerity and time[1].

PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV is a company operating in the construction and infrastructure sector. One important aspect in the success of the company is the work performance of employees. However, in recent times, there have been problems that need to be identified related to employee performance at PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV. The level of employee performance has decreased. This can occur due to various factors such as changes in policy, changes in the work environment, or mismatches between job demands and employee abilities. A decrease in job performance can have a negative impact on company productivity, quality of work, and customer satisfaction. There is a potential gap or imbalance between the company's expectations of employee motivation, teamwork and work discipline to achieve these expectations. Unmet expectations or mismatches between job duties and employee qualifications can hinder the achievement of optimal work performance.

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Teamwork can work best if each member can do the work and has the ability to: initiate discussions, seek information and opinions, propose procedures to achieve goals, elaborate opinions, conclude / summarize, test consensus, compromise and creatively resolve differences, try to lower tensions within the group, and express group feelings that will improve employee performance. In order for teams to work effectively in developing motivation, closeness, and productivity, many organizations view team building as one aspect of employee performance. According to [2] in organizations, teamwork is an important factor to improve employee performance because with this teamwork becomes a place to trust each other and build cohesiveness between organizational members.

In addition to teamwork, work discipline factors are very important in an organization, because with employee work discipline, an organization can achieve the goals of the work program it does. Work discipline is a very important part or variable in the development of human resource management therefore discipline is needed in an organization so that there is no negligence, deviation or negligence and ultimately waste in doing work. High work discipline of employees in a company shows the integrity and responsibility of employees to the company. With high work discipline, it makes it easier for companies to achieve their goals, if employees have work discipline, employees will work effectively and can save time at work so that there will be no deviations that can harm the company and can improve the work performance of the employees themselves. The level of discipline, both company discipline towards employees, and between employees towards the company is very necessary because through these disciplines will create a professional work climate. Complying with your own regulations as conveyed by [3] is one of the measuring tools and a reflection of work discipline.

Motivation is also needed in improving employee work performance. Motivation can also be interpreted as factors that direct and encourage a person's behavior or desire to carry out an activity expressed in the form of hard or weak effort. These factors are often referred to as motivation, as desired goals that drive people to behave in a certain way, so motivation is often also interpreted as wants, goals, needs or drives. Work motivation for employees is no less important, because motivation can direct and encourage employees to do high-performance work in accordance with company expectations. According to [4] Motivation is a set of reasons for performing certain actions. Motivation can be defined as the process that explains the intensity, direction and perseverance of a person in trying to achieve his goals.

1.1 Work Performance

Work Performance is the result of a person's work during a certain period compared to various possibilities such as standards, targets, or objectives or criteria that have been determined in advance and mutually agreed. Leaders must know the work performance of their subordinates in order to be able to make decisions that concern their employees. According to [5] work performance is the result of work that a person has achieved from his work behavior in carrying out work activities. According to [6] work performance is a result of work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him which is based on ability, experience and sincerity and time.

1.2 Team Work

According to [7] Team Work is a collection of individuals who work together to achieve a goal. According to [8] states that teamwork is a group whose individual efforts produce higher performance than the results obtained if the work is completed alone. Meanwhile, according to [9] teamwork, it is a group of individuals who work together to achieve similar goals and can be lighter to achieve these goals by working together rather than doing it alone. Working in a team will make it easier for members when experiencing some problems so that the team will function very well in solving these problems.

1.3 Work Discipline

Work discipline is defined as a person's attitude of obedience to a rule or provision that applies in an organization, namely joining the organization on the basis of awareness and realization, not because of an element of coercion. For a company, enforcing work discipline is very important. Because with the enforcement of work discipline in a company, it will ensure order and smoothness in the implementation of duties, so that the company can obtain optimal results. According to [10] Work discipline is a tool used by managers to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change a behavior and as an effort to increase awareness and willingness of someone to obey all company rules and social norms that apply. According to [6] Discipline is the awareness and willingness of a person who obeys all company regulations and applicable social norms.

1.4 Work Motivation

Every organization certainly wants to achieve goals. To achieve this goal, the role of humans involved in it is very important. According to [11] Motivation is a condition that encourages or becomes the cause of a person doing an action

or activity, which takes place consciously. According to [12] explaining motivation is an activity that results in, and maintains human behavior. While motivation according to [13] is a situation that motivates employees to achieve their goals, that is, motivation that can be said to be the energy that creates motivation itself.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Research Approach

The approach to this study uses quantitative methods. Quantitative research is a method to test certain theories by examining relationships between variables. According to [14] quantitative methods are research methods based on the philosophy of *positivism*, used to examine certain populations and samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative data analysis, with the aim of testing what has been set. This study uses quantitative data, namely data on the effect of Teamwork (X1) and Work Discipline with Work Motivation (Y2) on Work Performance (Y1) of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV Employees.

2.2 Population and Sample

To defining [14] population as a generalized area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions, so population is not only people, but includes all characteristics or subjects studied, but includes all characteristics or traits possessed by that subject. The population in this study is all contract employees contained in PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV totaling 140 respondents.

While the sample represents a portion of the population whose characteristics will be investigated and considered to be representative of the entire population or a smaller number of the population [14]. The technique used to determine the sample in this study is a simple random sampling technique. Simple random sampling technique is a technique of randomly sampling the population. To measure the size of the sample to be According studied, researchers use the Slovin formula, where this formula is able to measure the size of the sample to be studied. So, the number of samples used after rounding up was 58 respondents.

2.3 Data Analysis Techniques

In this study, data analysis used the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. PLS is a component-or variant-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) equation model. According to him [15], PLS is an alternative approach that shifts from a covariant-based SEM approach to a variant-based SEM that is covariance-based generally tests causality / theory while PLS is more predictive model. PLS is a powerful [15] method of analysis, because it is not based on many assumptions. For example, the data must be normally distributed, the sample does not have to be large. Besides being able to be used to confirm theories, PLS can also be used to explain the presence or absence of relationships between latent variables. PLS can simultaneously analyze constructs formed with reflective and formative indicators. According to [15] the purpose of PLS is to help researchers for prediction purposes. His formal model defines latent variables as linear aggregates of indicators. Weight estimates for creating latent variable score components are obtained based on how the inner model (a structural model that connects latent variables) and the outer model (a measurement model that is the relationship between indicators and their constructs) are specified. The result is the residual variance of the dependent variable. The stages of data analysis in this study are, as follows:

2.3.1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis provides an overview or description of each variable seen from the mean (*mean*), standard deviation, maximum and minimum values [15].

2.3.2 PLS (Partial Least Squares) Analysis

According to, [16] *Partial least square* analysis is a variant-based structural equation analysis (SEM) that can simultaneously perform measurement model testing as well as structural model testing. In processing this research data, PLS (*Partial Least Squares*) statistical tool software was used, namely Smart PLS version 3.2. Model evaluation in PLS-SEM using Smart PLS 3.2 can be done by assessing the results of model measurements (*outer model*), namely through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) by testing the validity and reliability of latent constructs, then continued with structural model evaluation and significance testing to test the influence between variable constructs. To analyze this research used several tests in PLS, namely: outer [15] *model evaluation* was carried out to assess validity and reliability [15]. It consists of convergent validity tests, discriminant validity and reliability tests using two methods, namely: *Cronbach's alpha* and *composite reliability* [16].

2.3.3 Path Diagram

The formation of path diagrams in the SEM process is a visualization of the conceptual framework of research so that it is easier to understand and learn (Sugiyono, 2013).. In addition, this path diagram will be tested through *goodness of fit* to see the suitability of the model to existing reality the formation of the path diagram must pay attention to the construct of exogenous or endogenous variables with manifest variables of each of these latent variables. The submission of the research structural equation model is, as follows:

$$Z = \rho_1 X_1 + \rho_2 X_2 + E_1$$

$$Y = \rho_3 X_1 + \rho_4 X_2 + \rho_5 Z + E_2$$

Where:

X1	= Teamwork
X2	= Work Discipline
Z	= Work Motivation
Y	= Work Performance
ρ	= Regression Coefficient Path
e	= Error Term

2.3.4 Measurement Model (Outer Model)

A research model cannot be tested in a prediction model of relational and causal relationships if it has not passed the purification stage in the measurement model. Measurement models are used to test construct validity and instrument reliability. Validity tests are carried out to determine the ability of research instruments to measure what should be measured. Reliability tests are used to measure the consistency of measuring instruments in measuring a concept or can also be used to measure the consistency of respondents in answering question items in questionnaires or research instruments. For construct validity tests, two methods are used, namely *convergent validity* and *discriminant validity* [16], while for reliability tests two methods are used, namely *Cronbach's Alpha* and *Composite Reliability*. *Cronbach's Alpha* measures the lower bound of the reliability value of a construct while *composite reliability* measures the true value of a construct's reliability. However, *composite reliability* is better at estimating the internal consistency of a construct.

2.3.5 Structural Model (Inner Model)

Structural models in PLS are evaluated using R² for dependent constructs, path coefficient values (β) or *t-values* for each *path* for interconstruct significance tests in structural models. The R² value is used to measure the degree of variation of the independent variable change against the dependent variable. The higher the R² value means the better the predictive model of the proposed research model. However, R² is not an absolute parameter in measuring the accuracy of prediction models because the theoretical basis of the relationship is the most important parameter to explain the causality relationship. The value of the path coefficient (β) or *inner model* indicates the level of significance in hypothesis testing. The *path* coefficient (β) score, or *inner model*, indicated by the T-statistic value, should be above 1.96 for the *two-tailed* hypothesis and above 1.64 for the *one-tailed* hypothesis for hypothesis testing at 5 percent alpha.

3. Results

3.1 Description of Research Respondents

The respondents used were 58 respondents of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV employees. The results of the data in this study were obtained from questionnaires distributed to respondents. The questionnaire in this study contains statement items related to research variables, the questionnaire also contains respondents' personal data consisting of names, gender, last education and length of work of respondents. The collected data from respondents are presented, as follows:

Table 1 Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics of Respondents	Total (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
1. Male	46	79.30%
2. Women	12	20.70%
Sum	58	100%
Age		
1. < 26 Years Old	7	12.10%
2. 26 - 35 years	22	37.90%
3. 36 - 45 years	23	39.70%
4. > 45 years old	6	10.30%
Sum	58	100%
Recent Education		
1. SMA/SMK	0	0%
2. Diploma (D1, D2, D3)	26	44.83%
3. Bachelor (S1)	32	55.17%
Sum	58	100%
Length of Work		
1. < 1 year	0	0%
2. 1 year - 5 years	19	32.80%
3. 6 years - 10 years	25	43.10%
4. > 10 years	14	24.10%
Sum	58	100%

Source: SPSS output version 25 (Data Processed by Author, 2023)

Table 1, shows that the gender of employees of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV is dominated by respondents with male gender as many as 46 respondents or 79.3% and women as many as 12 respondents or 20.70%. The age of employees of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV is dominated by the age of 36-45 years as many as 23 respondents or 39.7%. Age 26-35 years as many as 22 respondents or 37.9% and age > 40 years as many as 6 respondents or 10.30% and age <26 years as many as 7 respondents or 12.10%. The last education of employees of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV with high school education was 0 respondents or 0%. D3 education as many as 26 respondents or 44.83% and S1 education as many as 32 respondents or 55.17%. The length of work of employees of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV is dominated by working up to 1 year as many as 0 respondents or 0% and working over 1-5 years as many as 19 respondents or 32.8%. The length of work for 6-10 years was 25 respondents or as many as 43.10%. And the length of work > 10 years as many as 14 respondents or as many as 24.10%.

3.2 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis for each variable can be seen in the following table:

Based on the table, the minimum value of teamwork variables is 28.00, the maximum value is 40.00, the mean value is 35.14 and the std value. deviation of 2.941. The minimum value of the work discipline variable is 27.00, the maximum value is 36.00, the mean value is 31.81 and the std value. deviation of 2.639. The minimum value of the work motivation variable is 23.00, the maximum value is 32.00, the mean value is 28.03 and the std value. deviation of 2.248. The minimum value of the work performance variable is 15.00, the maximum value is 24.00, the mean value is 19.45 and the std value. deviation of 2.514.

Table 2 Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Kerjasama_Tim	58	28	40	35.14	2.941
Disiplin_Kerja	58	27	36	31.81	2.639
Motivasi_Kerja	58	23	32	28.03	2.248
Prestasi_Kerja	58	15	24	19.45	2.514
Valid N (listwise)	58				

Source: SPSS output version 25 (Data Processed by Author, 2023)

3.3 Outer Model or Measurement Model

There are three criteria in the use of data analysis techniques with SmartPLS to assess the outer model, namely convergent validity, discriminant validity and composite reliability.

3.3.1 Convergent Validity

The convergent validity assessment is based on the correlation between the estimated item score/component score and Software PLS. An individual's reflexive measure is said to be high if it correlates more than 0.70 with the measured construct. However, for the initial research of the development of a measurement scale, loading values of 0.5 to 0.6 are considered sufficient (Chin) in [15]. In this study, a loading factor limit of 0.60 will be used.

Source: SmartPLS Output version 4 (Data Processed by Author, 2023)

Figure 1 Early Stage Model

Table 1 Outer Loading

	Teamwork (KT)	Work Discipline (KT)	Work Motivation (MK)	Work Performance (PK)
KT1	0.899			
KT2	0.917			
KT3	0.942			
KT4	0.905			
KT5	0.772			
KT6	0.871			

DK1		0.924		
DK2		0.910		
DK3		0.915		
DK4		0.830		
DK5		0.894		
DK6		0.883		
MK1			0.845	
MK2			0.808	
MK3			0.853	
MK4			0.626	
MK5			0.705	
MK6			0.709	
PK1				0.861
PK2				0.866
PK3				0.821
PK4				0.868
PK5				0.919

Source: SmartPLS Output version 4 (Data Processed by Author, 2023)

Based on Table 1., the outer model value or correlation between the construct and the variable has met convergen validity because it has a loading factor value > 0.60 , in conclusion the construct for all variables can be used to test the hypothesis.

3.3.2 Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity is a good model if each loading value of each indicator of a latent variable has the greatest loading value with another loading value against other latent variables. The results of discriminant validity testing can be seen in the following table:

Table 2 Cross Loading

	Work Discipline (DK)	Teamwork (KT)	Work Motivation (MK)	Work Performance (PK)
DK1	0.924	0.120	0.195	0.333
DK2	0.910	0.191	0.141	0.308
DK3	0.915	0.152	0.191	0.298
DK4	0.830	0.149	0.166	0.269
DK5	0.894	0.172	0.183	0.233
DK6	0.883	-0.016	0.245	0.168
KT1	0.143	0.899	-0.038	0.107
KT2	0.127	0.917	-0.040	0.085
KT3	0.171	0.942	-0.068	0.193
KT4	0.034	0.905	0.013	0.134
KT5	0.133	0.772	0.057	0.047

KT6	0.189	0.871	0.059	0.091
MK1	0.197	-0.066	0.845	0.011
MK2	0.221	-0.034	0.808	-0.006
MK3	0.053	0.055	0.853	-0.011
MK4	0.091	0.044	0.626	-0.175
MK5	0.019	-0.021	0.705	0.011
MK6	0.094	0.044	0.709	-0.002
PK1	0.293	0.137	-0.064	0.861
PK2	0.319	0.132	0.090	0.866
PK3	0.098	0.036	-0.091	0.821
PK4	0.164	0.081	0.068	0.868
PK5	0.306	0.162	-0.120	0.919

Source: SmartPLS Output version 4 (Data Processed by Author, 2023)

Based on Table 2., it is known that the loading factor value for the latent variable indicator has a loading factor value greater than the loading value of other latent variables. That is, latent variables have good discriminant validity.

3.3.3 Cronbach's Alpha (CA), Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Validity and reliability criteria can also be seen from the value of Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability of a construct and the value of average variance extracted (AVE) of each construct. The construct is said to have Cronbach's alpha value over 0.60, composite reliability is high if the value is 0.70 and AVE is above 0.50. The results of cronbach's alpha, composite reliability and average variance extracted (AVE) can be seen in the following table:

Table 3 Cronbach's Alpha (CA), Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values

	Cronbach's alpha (CA)	Composite reliability (CR)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Teamwork (KT)	0.948	0.956	0.785
Work Discipline (DK)	0.949	0.959	0.798
Work Motivation (MK)	0.868	0.891	0.581
Work Performance (PK)	0.922	0.938	0.753

Source: SmartPLS output version 4 (Data Processed by Author, 2023)

Based on Table 3., it can be concluded that all constructs meet the reliable criteria, this is indicated by Cronbach's alpha value > 0.60, composite reliability > 0.70 and average variance extracted > 0.50 as recommended criteria.

3.4 Inner Model or Structural Model

The structural model or inner model is evaluated by looking at the percentage of variance described. The magnitude of the path coefficient value or inner model shows the magnitude of the influence of the exogenous latent variable on the endogenous latent variable. The value of *the standardized coefficient path* is indicated by a latent variable relationship arrow. If the value of *the standardized coefficient path* ≥ 0.1 , the influence of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable is significant (the greater the value, the greater the effect). The path coefficient score is indicated by the T-statistic value, where the value should be ≥ 1.96 for *two-tailed testing* and ≥ 1.64 for *one-tailed testing* at $\alpha = 5\%$ [18]. The stability of the estimation is tested with t-statistics through the *bootstrapping* procedure.

Source: SmartPLS Output version 4 (Data Processed by Author, 2023)

Figure 2 Influence Path Diagram Model Between Variables

3.5 Intervariable Analysis

The variables analyzed in this study are teamwork, work discipline, work motivation and work performance, each arranged by research indicators. The amount of influence or contribution of variables to each indicator can be seen in the Table, as follows:

Table 4 Influence on the Indicator of each Variable

	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
KT1 <- Teamwork (KT)	0.899	4.688	0.000
KT2 <- Teamwork (KT)	0.917	4.792	0.000
KT3 <- Teamwork (KT)	0.942	4.815	0.000
KT4 <- Teamwork (KT)	0.905	4.739	0.000
KT5 <- Teamwork (KT)	0.772	3.847	0.000
KT6 <- Teamwork (KT)	0.871	4.590	0.000
DK1 <- Work Discipline (DK)	0.924	22.899	0.000
DK2 <- Work Discipline (DK)	0.910	18.829	0.000
DK3 <- Work Discipline (DK)	0.915	20.686	0.000
DK4 <- Work Discipline (DK)	0.830	11.203	0.000
DK5 <- Work Discipline (DK)	0.894	15.347	0.000
DK6 <- Work Discipline (DK)	0.883	16.012	0.000
MK1 <- Work Motivation (MK)	0.845	4.593	0.000
MK2 <- Work Motivation (MK)	0.808	4.177	0.000
MK3 <- Work Motivation (MK)	0.853	5.169	0.000
MK4 <- Work Motivation (MK)	0.626	2.721	0.007

MK5 <- Work Motivation (MK)	0.705	4.019	0.000
MK6 <- Work Motivation (MK)	0.709	3.999	0.000
PK1 <- Work Performance (PK)	0.861	10.859	0.000
PK2 <- Work Performance (PK)	0.866	10.000	0.000
PK3 <- Work Performance (PK)	0.821	6.669	0.000
PK4 <- Work Performance (PK)	0.868	10.415	0.000
PK5 <- Work Performance (PK)	0.919	13.38	0.000

Source: SmartPLS Output version 4 (Data Processed by Author, 2023)

Based on Table 4., shows that each indicator of each variable has a value (P-Values < 0.05), meaning that each indicator has a positive and significant influence on the variables of this study.

3.5.1 Test Coefficient of Determination (R2)

The inner model can be measured by calculating the R-square for the dependent construct, the t-test as well as the significance of the structural path parameter coefficients. There are three categories in the grouping of R-square values. If the R-square value is 0.75 belongs to the strong category; for R-square values 0.50 belongs to the moderate category and 0.25 belongs to the weak category [19]. The R-square value can be seen in the following table:

Table 5 Test Results of Coefficient of Determination (R2)

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Work Motivation (MK)	0.146	0.017
Work Performance (PK)	0.113	0.072

Source: SmartPLS Output version 4 (Data Processed by Author, 2023)

Testing the *R square value as a model goodness-fit test* or alignment test described in Table 5. The work motivation variable has an *R-square* value of 0.146 after calculations through SmartPLS, this can be interpreted that the variance ability that can be explained by the variables of teamwork and work discipline against the variable of work motivation is 14.6%.

The work performance variable has an *R-square* value of 0.113 after calculations through SmartPLS, this can be interpreted that the variance ability that can be explained by the variables of teamwork and work discipline against the work performance variable is 11.3%.

3.5.2 Direct Influence

The hypothesis in the study will be tested statistically using the *bootstrapping method*. Hypothesis testing is done by looking at the value of the path coefficient which indicates the level of significance in hypothesis testing. The path coefficient score indicated by the T-statistic value must be greater than the t-value of the one-way test table (>1.64) with $\alpha = 5\%$. The p-values must be below $\alpha = 0.05$, so that the research hypothesis proposed in the study can be accepted.

Based on the results in Table 6., the results of the direct influence of teamwork on work motivation were obtained with a path coefficient value of -0.053 and (P-Values = 0.768 > 0.05) then H0 received H1 was rejected, meaning that there was no influence and no significant between teamwork on the work motivation of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV employees.

The result of the direct influence of teamwork on work performance with a path coefficient value of 0.101 and (P-Values = 0.448 > 0.05) then H0 received H2 received, meaning that there is a positive but not significant influence between teamwork on the work performance of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV employees.

The result of the direct influence of work discipline on work motivation with a path coefficient value of 0.216 and (P-Values = 0.254 > 0.05) then H0 rejected H31 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive but not significant influence between work discipline on the work motivation of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV employees.

Table 6 Direct Effect Test Results

	Path Coefficient	T-statistics >1.64	P values	Conclusion
Teamwork (KT) -> Work Motivation (MK)	-0.053	0.295	0.768	No effect and insignificant
Teamwork (KT) -> Work Performance (PK)	0.101	0.759	0.448	Positive and insignificant
Work Discipline (DK) -> Work Motivation (MK)	0.216	1.140	0.254	Positive and insignificant
Work Discipline (DK) -> Work Performance (PK)	0.291	2.177	0.030	Positive and significant
Work Motivation (MK) -> Work Performance (PK)	-0.096	0.599	0.549	No effect and insignificant

Source: SmartPLS Output version 4 (Data Processed by Author, 2023)

The result of the direct influence of work discipline on work performance with a path coefficient value of 0.291 and (P-Values = 0.030 < 0.05) then H0 rejected H4 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant influence between work discipline on the work performance of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV employees.

The result of the direct influence of work motivation on work performance with a path coefficient value of -0.096 and (P-Values = 0.549 > 0.05) then H0 received H5 rejected, meaning that there is no influence and insignificant between work motivation on the work performance of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV employees.

3.5.3 Indirect Influence

The output estimation results for indirect influence testing of structural models can be seen in the following table:

Table 7 Indirect Effect Test Results

	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Conclusion
Teamwork (KT) -> Work Motivation (MK) -> Work Performance (PK)	0.005	0.17	0.865	Positive and insignificant
Work Discipline (DK) -> Work Motivation (MK) -> Work Performance (PK)	-0.021	0.534	0.593	No effect and insignificant

Source: SmartPLS Output version 4 (Data Processed by Author, 2023)

Based on the results in Table 7., the results of the indirect influence of teamwork on work performance through work motivation with a path coefficient value of negative 0.005 and (P-Values = 0.865 > 0.05) then H0 rejected H7 is accepted, meaning that there is an influence but not significant between teamwork on work performance through the work motivation of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV employees.

The results of the indirect influence of work discipline on work performance through work motivation with a path coefficient value of negative 0.021 and (P-Values = 0.593 > 0.05) then H0 received H6 was rejected, meaning that there was no and insignificant influence between work discipline on work performance through the work motivation of PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zone IV employees.

4. Discussion

4.1 The Effect of Team Work on Work Motivation

Teamwork is one of the factors that can affect employee motivation. Employees who work in solid teams are more motivated to work, because they feel supported and share the same goals. However, the results of research conducted by PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV show that there is no influence and insignificance between teamwork on employee motivation. This means that teamwork cannot significantly increase employee motivation. Factors that can explain the insignificant influence between teamwork on employee motivation. One of the factors is the intrinsic factor, which is a factor that comes from within the employee. These intrinsic factors include the interests, talents, and needs of employees. Employees who have interests, talents, and needs that match their work will be more motivated to work, even if the teamwork is not very solid.

4.2 The Effect of Team Work on Work Performance

Teamwork is one of the factors that can affect employee work performance. Employees who work in a solid team will be more motivated to work, so they can produce more quality and timely products or services. However, the results of research conducted by PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV show that there is a positive but not significant influence between teamwork on employee work performance. This means that teamwork can improve employee performance, but the effect is not too great. There are several factors that can explain the positive but not significant influence of teamwork on employee performance. One of the factors is internal factors, which are factors that come from within employees. These internal factors include the employee's work ability, skills, and knowledge. Employees who have good work abilities, skills, and knowledge will be more motivated to work in teams, so they can improve their work performance.

4.3 The Effect of Work Discipline on Work Motivation

Work discipline is one of the factors that can affect employee motivation. Disciplined employees will be more compliant with work rules and procedures, so they can work more effectively and efficiently. This can increase employee motivation because they feel satisfied with the results of their work. However, the results of research conducted by PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV show that there is a positive but not significant influence between work discipline on employee work motivation. This means that work discipline can increase employee motivation, but the effect is not too great. Several factors can explain the positive but not significant influence between work disciplines on employee work motivation. One of the factors is the intrinsic factor, which is a factor that comes from within the employee. These intrinsic factors include the interests, talents, and needs of employees. Employees who have interests, talents, and needs that match their work will be more motivated to work, even though their work discipline is not too high.

4.4 The Effect of Work Discipline on Work Performance

Work discipline is one of the factors that can affect employee work performance. Disciplined employees will be more compliant with work rules and procedures, so they can work more effectively and efficiently. This can improve employee performance because they can produce more quality and timely products or services. The results of research conducted by PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV show that there is a positive and significant influence between work discipline on employee work performance. This means that work discipline can significantly improve employee performance. Several factors can explain the positive and significant influence between work discipline on employee work performance. One of the factors is internal factors, which are factors that come from within employees. These internal factors include the employee's work ability, skills, and knowledge. Employees who have good work abilities, skills, and knowledge will be more motivated to work with discipline, so they can improve their work performance.

4.5 The Effect of Work Motivation on Work Performance

Work motivation is one of the factors that can affect employee work performance. Employees who have high work motivation will be more motivated to work, so they can produce more quality and timely products or services. However, the results of research conducted by PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV show that there is no influence and insignificant between work motivation and employee work performance. This means that work motivation cannot significantly improve employee performance. Several factors can explain the insignificant influence between work motivation and employee performance. One of the factors is external factors, namely factors that come from outside the employee. These external factors include work system, work culture, and leadership. Employees who work in a work environment that is not conducive or have a bad leader, then their work motivation cannot be realized in the form of work performance.

4.6 The Effect of Team Work on Work Performance Through Work Motivation

Teamwork is one of the factors that can affect employee motivation. Employees who work in solid teams are more motivated to work, because they feel supported and share the same goals. High work motivation can encourage employees to work harder and be more productive. Motivated employees will be more eager to complete their tasks, and they will put more effort into producing quality products or services. Based on the results of research conducted by PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV, there is an influence but not significant between teamwork on work performance through employee work motivation. This means that teamwork can increase employee work motivation, and high work motivation can improve employee work performance, but the effect is not too great. Several factors can explain the influence but not significant between teamwork on work performance through employee work motivation. One of the factors is internal factors, which are factors that come from within employees. These internal factors include the employee's work ability, skills, and knowledge. Employees who have low work abilities, skills, and knowledge, then their work motivation cannot be realized in the form of high work performance.

4.7 The Influence of Work Discipline on Work Performance through Work Motivation

Work discipline is one of the factors that can affect employee motivation. Disciplined employees will be more compliant with work rules and procedures, so they can work more effectively and efficiently. This can increase employee motivation because they feel satisfied with the results of their work. High work motivation can encourage employees to work harder and be more productive. Motivated employees will be more eager to complete their tasks, and they will put more effort into producing quality products or services.

However, the results of research conducted by PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV show that there is no influence and insignificance between work discipline on work performance through employee work motivation. This means that work discipline cannot increase employee work motivation, and high work motivation cannot increase employee work performance through work discipline. Several factors can explain the influence and insignificance between work discipline on work performance through employee work motivation. One of the factors is external factors, namely factors that come from outside the employee. These external factors include work system, work culture, and leadership. Employees who work in a work environment that is not conducive or have a bad leader, then their work motivation cannot be realized in the form of work performance.

5. Conclusion

1. PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV also needs to make efforts to improve employee team work. These efforts can be done by:
 - Conduct socialization and training on the importance of teamwork to employees.
 - Provide opportunities for employees to work in teams
 - Rewarding employees who work well together.
2. PT HKI Binjai-Brandan Zona IV needs to make efforts to improve employee work discipline. These efforts can be done by:
 - Conduct socialization and training on the importance of work discipline to employees.
 - Supervise and evaluate the implementation of work discipline by employees.
 - Rewarding disciplined employees.
 - Sanction undisciplined employees.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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